

The Right to Adequate Housing Still In Outreach for the Persons with Disabilities.

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Abstract:

The right to adequate housing has been acknowledged as one of the fundamental right to an adequate standard of living ever since the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) was adopted in 1948. The right to adequate housing has now gained widespread acceptance as a fundamental human right granted to all people by several international .For the individuals with disabilities, the crucial aspects of leading a dignified, independent, and inclusive life involve making decisions about their living situation, being integrated within a community, and having readily available, suitable, and accessible housing. The inseparable and mutually reliant nature of the right to adequate housing alongside other fundamental human rights forms the core of the everyday reality for those with disabilities. “Having a safe and stable home, along with access to water, sanitation, community resources, and necessary support, can mean the distinction between survival and peril, safety and harm, and inclusion and loneliness. The paper proposes to explore the idea, key components, importance of the right to adequate housing, international laws and discussing the need for an human right approach and the measures likely to be taken for the effective realization of the right to adequate housing of the disabled people.

Introduction:

The Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) uses an inclusive definition of people with disabilities, which includes those who have long-term physical, mental, intellectual, or sensory impairments. These conditions, when combined with various obstacles, can potentially impede their complete and meaningful engagement in society, will not be at the same level as everyone else¹. Approximately 1.3 billion individuals, which accounts for about 16% of the world's population, currently live with a substantial disability². The Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) provides a more detailed explanation of what constitutes the right to adequate housing for individuals with disabilities.. In particular, the CRPD sets a new benchmark for realizing the right to adequate housing for people with disabilities, notably through Article 28³, which focuses on ensuring an acceptable standard of living and social protection. Many other provisions within the CRPD provide

further details and complexities regarding this entitlement. It also shows how the Convention amplifies and deepens the comprehension of this right. The ratification of the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities in 2006 represents a noteworthy shift in how society is required to view and integrate individuals with disabilities, guaranteeing their equitable participation alongside others. The Special Rapporteur on Adequate Housing has emphasized that the CRPD elucidates the entitlement to appropriate housing. This is accomplished by prioritizing principles of non-discrimination and substantial equality. Additionally, the CRPD includes distinctive provisions related to 'access to justice' and 'national implementation and monitoring'. These provisions are in place to guarantee that the principles of substantive equality are effectively put into practice through domestic legislation and policies⁴.

The CRPD constitutes legally binding international regulations. The expansive definition of individuals with disabilities outlined in Article 1⁵, the recognition that disability is a concept that evolves (as stated in the Preamble [e]), and the special attention given to women and children with disabilities in multiple articles, all contribute to a

¹ Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD),

² Disability, WHO ,March 7 2023, <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/disability-and-health>

³ States Parties recognize the right of persons with disabilities to an adequate standard of living for themselves and their families, including adequate food, clothing and housing, and to the continuous improvement of living conditions, and shall take appropriate steps to safeguard and promote the realization of this right without discrimination on the basis of disability

⁴ Farha, L. (2014). “Report of the Special Rapporteur on Adequate Housing” A/69/274, pp. 11–12, para. 41

⁵ Persons with disabilities include those who have long-term physical, mental, intellectual or sensory impairments which in interaction with various barriers may hinder their full and effective participation in society on an equal basis with others.

more comprehensive and nuanced perception of individuals with disabilities as a diverse group. This necessitates acknowledging the various layers of discrimination they face, the interconnection of various forms of oppression, and the mutual dependence of all human rights. This aligns with the concept of intersectionality, which posits that different forms of oppression are intertwined. As Andrew Solomon, an author and lecturer, pointed out, addressing sexism, for instance, cannot be achieved without also confronting racism. Following the same reasoning, any endeavor to attain suitable housing cannot be accomplished unless states, regions, and cities actively combat discrimination against individuals with disabilities. It is imperative to cultivate an understanding of the specific housing needs of individuals with disabilities and advocate for the right to housing through the enactment of legislation, implementation of policies, and execution of programs.

Essential Elements of right to adequate housing:

The right to suitable housing is intricate and underscores the interconnectedness and indivisibility of all human rights. The Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights has outlined seven dimensions of this right: (1) ensuring legal certainty of tenure; (2) providing services, materials, facilities, and infrastructure; (3) maintaining affordability; (4) ensuring habitability; (5) guaranteeing accessibility; (6) considering location; and (7) addressing cultural appropriateness⁶.

While these dimensions will be elaborated upon in the main body of this report, it is crucial to give heightened attention to ensuring that individuals with disabilities have access to housing that fulfills each of these criteria. The CRPD has added depth to each of these seven dimensions and has articulated specific factors that must be taken into account to guarantee that individuals with disabilities can exercise this right on an equal footing with others. States bear the responsibility of ensuring that individuals with disabilities have their right to adequate housing upheld. While the right to adequate housing, as outlined in the ICESCR, is subject to gradual fulfillment, States Parties are mandated to take action, both independently and through international aid and collaboration, particularly in economic and technical aspects, to the extent of their available resources, to realize this right. Efforts to enhance conditions and opportunities are necessary not only in response to

requests for assistance or reasonable accommodations from individuals with disabilities, but also as a fundamental part of applying the principle of universal design and reinstating the legal capacity of all persons with disabilities.

Housing advocates at various levels (international, national, regional, and local) frequently label specific segments of the population as 'vulnerable' in relation to their ability to secure their right to adequate housing. A fairly standard roster of 'vulnerable individuals' found in reports encompasses those in extreme poverty (including slum dwellers), women, individuals with non-heteronormative sexual orientations, migrants, refugees, persons with disabilities, stateless individuals, homeless individuals, people in institutional settings, ethnic or religious minorities, individuals in disaster-prone areas, and those exposed to conflict, among others. However, these identifications are often made in passing, lacking in-depth consideration. Additionally, rather than viewing these groups as inherently 'vulnerable', the emphasis should be on recognizing the systems and procedures that lead to the exclusion or marginalization of these groups. It's crucial to acknowledge how the various layers of one's identity affect their access to resources and opportunities, as well as whether they experience discrimination⁷.

Housing experiences of person with disabilities:

• Stigmatization, discrimination and criminalization of disabled people:

Individuals with disabilities often face a challenging housing experience, as they encounter widespread negative beliefs that portray disability as something abnormal, inferior, or associated with illness. This often leads people with disabilities to limit their social interactions and stay indoors because or out of fear of encountering stigma or potential harm. Housing solutions specifically tailored for those with psychosocial or intellectual disabilities are frequently met with opposition from local communities from the people even though from their family members itself, and residents in such facilities often find themselves isolated or disregarded by their neighbors⁸. When individuals with disabilities search for housing, whether in the private or public sector, they often face both overt and subtle forms of discrimination from others

⁶ The Right to Adequate Housing, Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights, UNHabitat, FactSheetNo.,21/Rev.1, https://www.ohchr.org/sites/default/files/Documents/Publications/FS21_rev_1_Housing_en.pdf

⁷ World Health Organization (2014), Draft WHO global disability action plan 2014–2021: Better health for all people with disability, 13 November 2015, <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/who-global-disability-action-plan-2014-2021>

⁸ United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF), "Children and young people with disabilities", fact sheet (May 2013), www.unicef.org/disabilities/files/Factsheet_A5_Web_NEW.pdf

because of the inability. There are situations where access to housing is unfairly withheld based on unwarranted concerns about potential harm to the property. In many countries, income and employment status are used as criteria to assess potential tenants, categorizing well-paid, full-time workers without disabilities as "eligible" for affordable rental housing, while those with disabilities and lower incomes are denied this opportunity. The criminalization of individuals with disabilities, especially those experiencing homelessness or with psychosocial disabilities, is a widespread occurrence. It is a typical pattern for individuals with psychosocial disabilities to first lose their housing due to unmet needs or insufficient financial support, then to face criminalization within the context of homelessness, and ultimately to end up incarcerated.

- **Institutionalization and deprivation of choice of the disabled people:**

Institutionalization stands as a clear example of how the right to adequate housing is violated when disability is erroneously seen through a medical perspective or an illness. Placing individuals with disabilities in isolated settings, under strict social supervision, is justified under the guise of providing "treatment" or "care." This approach frequently combines harsh living conditions with significant restrictions on personal autonomy, as well as the imposition of severe and inhumane treatment, which may include instances of physical and sexual abuse. Forced institutionalization often arises as an indirect consequence of other infringements on the right to adequate housing. Often even the family members were forcing these disabled one to moving to the care centers. When states neglect to offer essential forms of support for living within the community, or when individuals with disabilities or their families lack the means to afford housing, individuals with disabilities may be compelled to reside in institutions due to a scarcity of housing alternatives or options⁹.

- **Homelessness:**

Individuals with disabilities are disproportionately affected by homelessness. This sets off a harmful cycle where disability often leads to homelessness, and in return, experiencing homelessness can lead to the emergence or exacerbation of impairments and further challenges linked to societal discrimination and isolation. The Special Rapporteur has introduced a fresh

⁹ Thematic study on the right of persons with disabilities to live independently and be included in the community, United Nations A/HRC/28/37 General Assembly, 12 December 2014, <https://documents-dds-ny.un.org/doc/UNDOC/GEN/G14/241/66/PDF/G1424166.pdf?OpenElement>

perspective centered on rights, viewing homelessness not just as a deficiency of housing (both in terms of physical and social dimensions) but also as a socially constructed group identity that is intertwined with marginalization and prejudice, much of which is based on preconceived beliefs about individuals with disabilities¹⁰.

- **Inadequate or informal settlements and homeless encampment:**

In urban areas, individuals with disabilities facing poverty often live in makeshift shelters or homeless encampments. The Special Rapporteur on the right to adequate housing has been profoundly troubled by the deplorable living conditions endured by these individuals. This encompasses young children and elderly individuals who endure isolation, sometimes confined to dimly lit rooms without access to electricity, hidden away at the back of their homes, and lacking access to community centers, social interactions, or healthcare facilities. Additionally, access to water, sanitation, and hygiene facilities is often unavailable and situated at a considerable distance from their homes¹¹ where the disabled one will not have a way to access when comparing with others.

- **Natural Calamities, conflict and other humanitarian situations:**

The widespread displacement caused by perilous circumstances like armed conflicts, humanitarian emergencies, and natural disasters has serious consequences for people with disabilities. As per a United Nations study, a mere 20 percent of individuals with disabilities could swiftly leave their homes without encountering hindrances in an emergency. This indicates that a disproportionately large number of them would be at risk of injury or even loss of life during a disaster due to insufficient support from organized relief efforts.

- **Human rights-based approach to disability in CRPD:**

Article 3(a)¹² of the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities emphasizes the importance of upholding fundamental principles such as inherent dignity, individual autonomy of the disabled people, including their right to make

¹⁰ Report of the Special Rapporteur on the rights of persons with disabilities, United Nations A/HRC/34/58 General Assembly, <https://documents-dds-ny.un.org/doc/UNDOC/GEN/G16/436/64/PDF/G1643664.pdf?OpenElement,20> december 2016

¹¹ The right to adequate housing for people with disabilities living in cities, UN Habitat, United nation human right, 2015, file:///D:/SEMINAR%20AND%20PUBLICATION/Di sability%20Report.pdf

¹² Respect for inherent dignity, individual autonomy including the freedom to make one's own choices, and independence of persons

independent choices, and personal independence has been mentioned. This principle holds significant weight in interpreting the right to suitable housing. For individuals with disabilities, being deprived of the choice regarding where and with whom they live is often the most profound infringement on their dignity and autonomy. Article 28¹³ underscores the critical role of equality and non-discrimination in realizing the right to housing for persons with disabilities. States are obligated to take affirmative steps, to the extent of their available resources, in addressing systemic homelessness and housing deprivation, which disproportionately affects this group. They should strive towards fully realizing the right to adequate housing for all individuals with disabilities.

Article 9¹⁴ of the Convention is a unique provision that outlines the obligation of States to identify and eliminate barriers and ensure accessibility, and it holds particular importance in the context of housing. Participation is integral to implementing the right to housing for persons with disabilities. Article 4(3)¹⁵ emphasizes that States must engage closely with and actively involve individuals with disabilities and their representative organizations when implementing legislation, policies, or other decisions. Additionally, under Article 13, persons with disabilities must have effective access to justice at all stages of legal proceedings, on an equal basis with others. States are urged to ensure this access

¹³ States Parties recognize the right of persons with disabilities to an adequate standard of living for themselves and their families, including adequate food, clothing and housing, and to the continuous improvement of living conditions, and shall take appropriate steps to safeguard and promote the realization of this right without discrimination on the basis of disability.

¹⁴ To enable persons with disabilities to live independently and participate fully in all aspects of life, States Parties shall take appropriate measures to ensure to persons with disabilities access, on an equal basis with others, to the physical environment, to transportation, to information and communications, including information and communications technologies and systems, and to other facilities and services open or provided to the public, both in urban and in rural areas. These measures, which shall include the identification and elimination of obstacles and barriers to accessibility, shall apply to, *inter alia*

¹⁵ In the development and implementation of legislation and policies to implement the present Convention, and in other decision-making processes concerning issues relating to persons with disabilities, States Parties shall closely consult with and actively involve persons with disabilities, including children with disabilities, through their representative organizations

for claims related to the right to suitable housing for individuals with disabilities, establish mechanisms for complaints and accountability, and ensure that courts are authorized and adequately equipped to hear and adjudicate such claims.

ICESCR and disability:

The entitlement to housing, which constitutes a part of the broader "right to a decent standard of living," traces its roots back to Article 25 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights¹⁶. The International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR), endorsed by the General Assembly on December 16, 1966, formalized this right within a legal framework¹⁷. Article 2 of the Covenant contains an anti-discrimination provision and requires States Parties to take measures, both independently and through international aid and cooperation, particularly in economic and technical aspects, to the fullest extent of their available resources, with the aim of progressively realizing the complete fulfillment of the rights enshrined in the Covenant¹⁸. This entitlement was further elucidated and specified in various general remarks made by the Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (CESCR). General Comment 4, issued in 1991, dealt with the use of male pronouns in the original text and clarified that the term "family" should be interpreted broadly. The Committee has described the right to suitable housing as "the right to reside somewhere with security, tranquility, and dignity." "In its General Comment 5, the CESCR specifically addressed the rights of individuals with disabilities.

This encompassed a broad statement asserting that the living conditions of persons with disabilities are often so dire in many parts of the world that the provision of essentials like food, water, shelter, health, protection, and education should be at the forefront of national initiatives. This

¹⁶ 3 UDHR, Article 25 (1), "Everyone has the right to a standard of living adequate for the health and well-being of himself and of his family, including food, clothing, housing and medical care and necessary social services, and the right to security in the event of unemployment, sickness, disability, widowhood, old age or other lack of livelihood in circumstances beyond his control."

¹⁷ ICESCR, Article 11, (1): "The States Parties to the present Covenant recognize the right of everyone to an adequate standard of living for himself and his family, including adequate food, clothing and housing, and to the continuous improvement of living conditions. The States Parties will take appropriate steps to ensure the realization of this right, recognizing to this effect the essential importance of international co-operation based on free consent."

¹⁸ 7 CESCR (1994), General Comment 5 (Eleventh session), Persons with Disabilities, E/1995/22 (1994), <https://www.refworld.org/pdfid/4538838f0.pdf>

concern extended not only to so-called developing nations but also to countries with relatively high living standards¹⁹. The CESCR proposed an expansive definition of discrimination related to disability, encompassing any form of differentiation, exclusion, limitation, or preference, or the refusal of reasonable accommodation based on disability, which has the effect of negating or impairing the acknowledgment, enjoyment, or exercise of economic, social, or cultural rights. Additionally, they highlighted that housing is one of the sectors where discrimination against disabilities is most keenly felt²⁰. Furthermore, the acknowledgment of the necessity to offer appropriate personal assistance and support services was affirmed as an integral component of the inherent right to housing. This support is intended to aid individuals in enhancing their level of self-sufficiency in their daily lives and in exercising their entitlement.

Core elements of the right to adequate housing for the persons with disabilities:

The Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights in its general comment no 4 (1991) identified key factors to be considered in determining if housing is adequate

- **Security of Tenure:** The fundamental right to housing hinges on having a stable and secure living situation. Individuals with disabilities often face a higher likelihood of lacking this security, and they frequently endure devastating consequences due to displacement and forced removal from their homes. This not only involves losing their physical residence but also the network of support and connections crucial for their well-being. States have an obligation to establish legal protections against any form of involuntary eviction, whether it occurs in formal housing agreements, ownership arrangements, or informal settlements²¹.

- **Affordability:** The primary challenge in securing housing rights for individuals with disabilities often arises from their inability to afford suitable accommodations within their resources or income. Governments are tasked with eliminating not only physical barriers, but also financial and legal obstacles that hinder access to appropriate housing for individuals with disabilities. This entails ensuring that rents, utilities, and essential services are financially accessible, achieved through the provision of necessary financial assistance, which may include rental subsidies. Additionally, governments must address barriers related to rental

agreements and access to loans²² should be provided and with considering their inabilities.

- **Availability of Services:** Having access to necessary services is crucial for independent living and having agency over where and how to live in the community. Access to water and sanitation is a pressing concern for many persons with disabilities²³.

- **Habitability:** Ensuring a safe environment free from violence or mistreatment is crucial for habitability for individuals with disabilities. Additionally, making adaptations to the physical environment may be necessary to ensure livability, such as implementing measures to reduce noise in apartments for individuals with disabilities²⁴.

- **Location:** Individuals with disabilities often have specific requirements regarding the placement of their residences to ensure accessibility to employment, convenient transportation, necessary support, and healthcare facilities. The trend of relocating low-income communities to the outskirts of urban areas has had a disproportionately negative impact on people with disabilities. These acts of displacement and isolation go against the housing rights and other fundamental human rights of individuals with disabilities.

Cultural adequacy- For many individuals with disabilities, their cultural identity and expression are essential for their personal fulfillment and meaningful integration within their communities. It is the duty of states to provide housing in a manner that allows persons with disabilities to embrace their cultural identity and actively participate in the cultural advancement of their communities²⁵.

Conclusions and recommendations:

Few marginalized groups experience such severe breaches of their housing rights as individuals with disabilities. Worldwide, they frequently face homelessness, institutionalization, and unjustifiable mistreatment solely because of their disability. They contend with isolation, prejudice, and unfair treatment in all facets of housing, including accessibility, design, and the development and execution of policies. Their very lives are jeopardized by housing and communities that prioritize exclusion and homogeneity over inclusion and diversity. However, it is from these experiences and the assertion of equal dignity and rights by those affected that the disability human rights paradigm has emerged. This paradigm holds

¹⁹ Supra note 11

²⁰ Supra note 11

²¹ Miloon Kothari, Sabrina Karmali & Shivani Chaudhry, *The Human Right to Adequate Housing and Land*, NATIONAL HUMAN RIGHTS COMMISSION, 2006, <https://nhrc.nic.in/sites/default/files/Housing.pdf>

²² Supra note 16

²³ Supra note 16

²⁴ Supra note 16

²⁵ CESCR General Comment No. 4: The Right to Adequate Housing (Art. 11 (1) of the Covenant) adopted at the Sixth Session of the Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, 13 December 1991, <https://www.refworld.org/pdfid/47a7079a1.pdf>

the potential to invigorate the right to adequate housing by emphasizing and magnifying its core principle: having a place to live with dignity. It enables individuals with disabilities to actively engage in their communities and acknowledges diversity as a strength that fosters thriving households and communities.

- Give priority to and enshrine in national legislation the duty to fulfill the right to housing for individuals with disabilities to the fullest extent possible, linking this legal responsibility to the commitment to ensure suitable housing for everyone.
- Establish non-discrimination provisions, policies and schemes rooted in substantive equality, acknowledging the affirmative duties to tackle the systemic housing disparities experienced by individuals with disabilities;
- Guarantee that all individuals with disabilities have the opportunity to live without being confined to institutions, and that access to adequate housing, essential services, and appropriately trained assistance is provided within the community and should ensure all the elements of right to adequate housing is met.
- Assure access to a fair legal process and effective mechanisms for accountability in cases involving claims to the right to adequate housing by individuals with disabilities, including situations where States have failed to implement reasonable programmatic measures to realize this right and should be given proper awareness of their right.
- Establish a well-defined policy framework that actively includes individuals with disabilities across all aspects of housing policy and design. This framework should give special consideration to those facing poverty or homelessness, as well as prioritize the needs of women, ethnic, religious, or linguistic minorities, indigenous communities, migrants, and people of all age groups.
- Conduct thorough and comprehensive data collection efforts regarding the housing situations of individuals with disabilities. This should involve both qualitative and quantitative methods, and the data should be classified using the standard survey questions provided by the Washington Group on Disabilities.
- Address the pressing issue of homelessness among individuals with disabilities as a top priority. Put particular emphasis on implementing measures to enhance the living conditions of those residing in informal settlements and homeless encampments.
- Non-governmental organizations and associations representing individuals with disabilities should either lead or support legal

actions against systemic breaches of the right to housing of individuals with disabilities, and seek comprehensive remedies.

- Establish and enforce legal protections for housing, including ensuring secure tenure, in a manner that recognizes and accommodates the distinct needs of individuals with disabilities.
- Guarantee that all individuals with disabilities have the capability to exercise their legal rights pertaining to the right to suitable housing. This includes enabling them to access and engage in contracts for credit and leases.
- It is imperative to guarantee that individuals who are refugees, internally displaced, or migrants and have disabilities, are able to enjoy their entitlement to suitable housing. This can be achieved by incorporating pertinent international human rights provisions into the upcoming global agreements on refugees and safe, organized, and regular migration.
- It is crucial to ensure that local authorities implement and uphold the right to housing in all their activities, encompassing urban planning, zoning, transportation planning, as well as the creation and upkeep of housing

Courts, tribunals, and national human rights institutions should:

Interpret and apply national legislation in a manner consistent with the right to adequate housing for individuals with disabilities. Specifically, they should acknowledge that the rights to life, liberty, substantive equality, and non-discrimination necessitate that governments address homelessness, offer support for community living, and cater to the varied housing requirements of individuals with disabilities.(ii) Guarantee access to legal recourse and effective accountability for all facets of governmental obligations regarding the right to housing of individuals with disabilities. This includes allocations of financial resources and the efficacy of strategies and programs.

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